

Ternary Complexes of Cadmium(II) with Amino Acids and Xylenol Orange

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Manuscript received 12 May 1992, revised 1 February 1993, accepted 9 February 1993

Calvin-Bjerrum's potentiometric technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti has been used to study the interaction of Cd^{II} with xylenol orange and amino acids to form mixed-ligand complexes. Xylenol orange (XO) is chosen as primary ligand whereas some amino acids (L), viz. L- α -alanine, L-serine, DL-methionine and glycine are chosen as secondary ligands. The proton-ligand stability constant evaluated for the amino acids is found to follow the order : L- α -alanine > DL-methionine > L-serine \approx glycine. Herewith the $\log K_{Cd(II)(XO)L}^{Cd(II)XO}$ values have also been evaluated. The mixed-ligand stability constant values are found to follow the order : glycine > L-serine \approx L- α -alanine > DL-methionine.

Cadmium(II) shows the carcinogenic effect and its compounds are also notorious for their toxic effect on bones¹. The literature survey reveals that xylenol orange (XO) has been extensively used as an indicator and as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of a large number of metal ions and shows a very good complexing behaviour in solution as well as in solid². Since xylenol orange contains a number of coordinating sites, so it was thought of interest to evaluate the interaction of various amino acids on Cd^{II}-XO complex in solution.

In continuation of our work, we have chosen xylenol orange as primary ligand and L- α -alanine, glycine, DL-methionine and L-serine as secondary ligands, and studied the interaction of these ligands with Cd^{II}. The present communication deals with the potentiometric approach to determine the stability constants of the mixed-ligand complexes of Cd^{II}. The modified method of Irving and Rossotti has been applied to determine $\log K_{Cd(II)(XO)L}^{Cd(II)XO}$. All studies were performed at a constant ionic strength of 0.1 M (KNO₃) and at 25 \pm 0.1 $^\circ$. The order of stability constants have been discussed on the basis of steric hinderance attributed by secondary ligands in the formation of mixed-ligand complex.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants of secondary

ligands : The values of \bar{n}_A at various pH-meter readings were calculated from acid and ligand titration curves for secondary ligands. A graph is plotted between \bar{n}_A vs pH (Fig. 2a) and proton-ligand stability constants were evaluated by (i) the method of interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values and (ii) the method of interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values³. The values obtained at $\mu = 0.1$ M (KNO₃) for all these secondary ligands are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE I – PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Temp. = 25 \pm 0.1 $^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1$ M (KNO ₃)				
Ligand	pK/log K ^a	Method (i)	Method (ii)	Lit. value (Temp. $^\circ$ C)
L- α -Alanine	$\log K_1^H$	9.90	9.91	9.87 (25)
Glycine	$\log K_1^H$	9.75	9.75	9.77 (25)
DL-Methionine	$\log K_1^H$	9.35	9.38	9.28 (20)
L-Serine	$\log K_1^H$	9.30	9.32	9.12 (20)
[Cd ^{II} -(XO)-Alanine]	$\log K^*$	3.15	3.12	
[Cd ^{II} -(XO)-Glycine]	$\log K^*$	3.30	3.37	
[Cd ^{II} -(XO)-Serine]	$\log K^*$	3.17	3.20	
[Cd ^{II} -(XO)-Methionine]	$\log K^*$	3.10	3.12	
^a $\log K^* = \log K_{Cd(II)-(XO)-L}^{Cd(II)-XO}$				

Fig. 1. Titration curve for Cd^{II}-XO-serine mixed-ligand complex at 25° and μ = 0.1M (KNO₃).

Metal-ligand stability constants : The formation constants have been obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL (Fig. 2b). Values of \bar{n} (the average number of ligand molecule attached per metal ion) were calculated taking into consideration the difference from curves (A) and (B), from which the difference of curves (C) and (D) is subtracted at various pH values, and pL (the free ligand exponent) values were evaluated by the equation given by Irving and Rossotti⁴.

From the titration curves (Fig. 2 as an example) it is revealed that the primary complex formation (curve C) takes place at very low pH and the calculation shows that it is stable upto pH 10.2. Mixed-ligand complex curve (D) shifts slightly towards left of the primary ligand complex curve (C) favouring the zwitterion structure of amino acids⁵,

In acidic medium NH₂ group takes up a proton and this causes pH of the solution to increase. Between pH 4.5 and 6.0 the curves (C) and (D) overlap each other indicating that in this range, where primary ligand combines with Cd^{II}, attachment of secondary ligand does not take place. The mixed complex (curve D) separates from primary ligand complex curve (C) at pH about 6.1 due to self-

Fig. 2. (a) Ligand dissociation curve and (b) Formation curve for (Cd^{II}-XO-serine)

dissociation of the secondary ligand. After pH 6.3 mixed complex curve indicates the attachment of secondary ligands and the formation of [Cd-XO-(OH)_n] is also suppressed. It is however necessary to clear at this point that the stability constants here are really not overall mixed-ligand stability constants but these are stepwise formation constants. The equilibria may assumed as

The charges have been omitted for the sake of simplicity.

Table 1 gives the summary of the results obtained in the present work. The proton-ligand stability constant was found to follow the order : L-α-alanine > glycine > DL-methionine ≈ L-serine, which is well in the agreement with literature values obtained by other workers⁶.

The stability constants were found to follow the order : glycine > L-serine ≈ L-α-alanine > DL-methionine. Since glycine has no bulky substituent on α-carbon atom hence it can form rather stable and strainless chelates, the less stability of L-α-alanine and L-serine may be due to steric hinderance attributed by bulky substituent present on α-carbon atom.

Experimental

Stock solutions of metal nitrates (AnalaR) were prepared in double-distilled water. The metal content was estimated by EDTA titration⁷. A 0.002 M HNO₃ (A.R.) and CO₂-free 0.01 M NaOH (A.R., C.D.H.) were prepared in double-distilled water. Solutions (0.001 M) of ligands were prepared in double-distilled water. Xylenol orange (A.R., C.D.H.) was purified before use⁸ and its 1.0 × 10⁻³ M solution was prepared in double-distilled water.

A Systronics 331 pH meter was used with glass-calomel electrode assembly. All the experiments were done at 25±0.1°. Constant ionic strength (0.1 M) was maintained by KNO₃ and an inert atmosphere was created by bubbling nitrogen through the solution throughout the course of titration.

Procedure : The following four mixtures were prepared : (A) 5 ml HNO₃ (2.0 × 10⁻³ M); (B) 5 ml HNO₃ (2.0 × 10⁻³ M) + 5 ml secondary ligand (1.0 × 10⁻³ M); (C) 5 ml HNO₃ (2.0 × 10⁻³ M) + 5 ml primary ligand (1.0 × 10⁻³ M) + 5 ml metal solution (1.0 × 10⁻³ M); (D) 5 ml HNO₃ (2.0 × 10⁻³ M) + 5 ml primary ligand (1.0 × 10⁻³ M) + 5 ml secondary ligand (1.0 × 10⁻³ M) + 5 ml metal solution (1.0 × 10⁻³ M). These mixtures were prepared in such a manner that the concentrations of common ingredients were identical in each case. An appropriate amount of KNO₃ was added to maintain the constant ionic strength (0.1 M). The total volume of all systems (40 ml) were kept identical by adding double-distilled water. A graph between pH-meter reading and volume of alkali added was plotted. The four titration curves obtained were referred to as (A) acid curve, (B)

secondary ligand curve, (C) primary complexation curve, and (D) mixed-ligand complexation curve.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to record their sincere thanks to Prof. P. K. Srivastava, Head of Department, Department of Chemistry, B.H.U., for facilities and continuous encouragement in accomplishing this work.

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